

Microstructure and Mechanical Properties of Biomedical Co-Cr-Mo Alloy Produced by Precision Casting and 3D Printing Technologies

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Cobalt-based alloys are widely used for orthopedic implants due to their excellent mechanical properties and corrosion resistance. Biomedical Co-Cr-Mo alloy, commonly applied in knee replacements, is typically produced by precision casting. However, in cases requiring patient-specific geometries, additive manufacturing technologies, such as Selective Laser Melting (SLM), offer promising alternatives. This study compares the microstructure and mechanical properties of Co-Cr-Mo alloy in the as-cast state and after SLM processing. The SLM-produced samples exhibited a fine, cellular microstructure and superior mechanical strength. Specifically, the printed alloy achieved a yield strength of 688 ± 8 MPa and an ultimate tensile strength of 994 ± 11 MPa, exceeding that of the cast material by about 495 ± 1 MPa. These results demonstrate the potential of SLM technology for manufacturing customized orthopedic implants with improved mechanical properties and dimensional accuracy.

Keywords: Cobalt-based alloys, mechanical properties, 3D printing, selective laser melting, microstructure.

1 Introduction

Cobalt-based alloys are widely used for orthopedic implants due to their excellent mechanical properties and corrosion resistance. The biomedical alloy Co-Cr-Mo, commonly used in knee replacements, is typically manufactured by precision casting [1]. This technology enables the production of castings with complex geometries with very good surface quality. It consists of several steps, such as the preparation of a meltable model and mold, followed by burnout of the model, after which the actual casting process can take place. For this reason, changing the shape of the casting is very time-consuming.

Nowadays, 3D printing technologies are increasingly used for the production of complex-shaped components. The most frequently used method is Selective Laser Melting (SLM), which involves depositing a layer of powder in a powder bed and then scanning it with a laser in areas where the powder is to be melted. The result is a compact product with the desired geometry, a very fine microstructure, and good mechanical properties [2, 3].

This research investigates the potential for partially replacing investment casting with SLM technology in the production of Co-Cr-Mo knee implants. Both technologies offer specific advantages and in special cases, for example, custom-made implants, 3D printing may be more suitable. To evaluate this possibility, a comprehensive analysis of the microstructure and mechanical properties of both cast and 3D printed Co-Cr-Mo alloy was carried out.

2 Experimental Methods

In this work, the properties of Co-28Cr-6Mo alloy, with a chemical composition conforming to the ASTM F75 standard, prepared by precision casting and 3D printing, were compared. For the characterization of the cast state, a real knee implant manufactured by the company Prospan spol. s.r.o. (Kladno, Czech Republic), specifically a femoral implant (see Fig. 1 a) was used, and the 3D printed alloy was prepared by Comtes FHT a.s. (Dobruška, Czech Republic). For the preparation of printed materials, SLM technology was used, employing the AconityTWO device with a 250 W laser and a scanning speed of 1000 mm s^{-1} . The printed samples were prepared directly as dogbone-shaped samples for tensile mechanical property testing (see Fig. 1 b).

Fig. 1 Total knee implant image (a) and schema of prepared SLM printed samples (b).

For a comprehensive description of the structure, the phase composition of both samples was determined using X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis. A PANalytical X'Pert Pro device with a Co cathode ($\lambda = 1.78901 \cdot 10^{-10}$ m) was used for this purpose. Furthermore, the microstructure was observed using an optical microscope (OM, Nikon MA100) and a scanning electron microscope (SEM, Tescan Mira 2) equipped with energy (EDS, Oxford Instruments). Before observation, the samples were polished and then etched in concentrated aqua regia for 2 minutes. To characterize the printed material's microstructure, two samples were prepared – in the XY direction and the XZ direction.

To determine the mechanical properties, Vickers hardness measurements were first performed under a load of 1 kg for 10 s. A total of 10 measurements were performed and statistically evaluated, including a confidence interval at a 95% significance level. In addition, tensile testing was carried out using an Instron 5882 device. The loading speed, determined according to the standard, was $v = 1.68 \text{ mm/s}$. Testing was performed three times for each material.

3 Results and Discussion

In terms of phase composition, there were small differences between the materials (Fig. 2 a). While the SLM printed alloy was composed of 70 wt.% fcc phase and 30 wt.% hcp phase, the cast sample also showed the presence of 65 wt.% of fcc phase, 33 wt.% of hcp phase, and 2 wt.% carbides corresponding to Cr_{23}C_6 . In general, these materials often contain a combination of the majority fcc and minority hcp phases, the content of which is around 25-30% [4]. The proportion of the hcp phase also depends on the cooling rate of the material during production. At lower cooling rates, the phase transformation from the fcc structure to the hcp occurs in a larger proportion [5-8].

Fig. 2 Results of phase composition analysis (a) and results of Vickers hardness (b) for cast and SLM printed Co-Cr-Mo alloy.

The distribution of individual phases in the structure of the cast Co-Cr-Mo alloy can be observed in the microstructure image from optical microscopy (see Fig. 3), where a distinct dendritic structure is evident. While the dendrites are formed by the hcp phase, carbides surrounded by a phase with an fcc crystal lattice occur in the interdendritic sites. Thanks to SEM + EDS analysis, the distribution of chemical elements in the carbide particles was determined (see Fig. 3). These results show that it is a mixture of chromium and molybdenum carbides, which is often referred to as mixed carbide M₂₃C₆ [9]. Overall, the investigated structure in the cast state corresponded to previous research [4, 10, 11].

In contrast, the Co-Cr-Mo alloy prepared by SLM exhibits a structure typical for 3D printed materials (see Fig. 4). In the XY direction, traces of laser scanning are visible, while in the XZ direction, individual printing layers can be observed in the form of melt pools. So-called epitaxial grains then extend across the melt pools. Upon closer observation with a scanning electron microscope, a fine-grained cellular substructure was visible in both directions, which is created as a result of a high cooling rate and the concentration gradient during solidification [12]. Unlike the as-cast state, no carbide particles were detected. The overall microstructure of SLM printed alloy is also significantly more homogeneous and fine-grained.

Fig. 3 Microstructure of cast Co-Cr-Mo alloy observed via OM (a, b) and SEM + EDS (c).

Fig. 4 Microstructure of SLM printed Co-Cr-Mo alloy in XZ direction (a, c) and XY direction (b, d) observed via OM (a, b) and SEM (c, d).

In terms of mechanical properties, the Vickers hardness of the materials was first measured, the results of which are shown in Fig. 2 b. These results show that the cast Co-Cr-Mo alloy showed a lower hardness of 328 ± 6 HV 1 than the alloy prepared by SLM technology. The printed material showed approximately 15% higher hardness in both the XY and XZ directions, with the influence of directionality being very small. It was further found that the SLM printed material prepared in this research showed a higher hardness than reported in the literature for Co-Cr-Mo alloy prepared by sintering technology, which is usually 350 HV [4, 13].

Large differences between the two technologies were also observed in the course of tensile tests (see Fig. 5). The cast sample measured a tensile yield strength of 457 ± 5 MPa and a tensile strength of 494 ± 1 MPa, along with a relatively high ductility of 39 ± 17 %. In contrast, the 3D printed material achieved higher strength, specifically a tensile yield strength of 688 ± 8 MPa and an ultimate tensile strength of 994 ± 11 MPa. Such high mechanical properties are mainly due to the fine-grained structure, which is typical for materials prepared by SLM technology. Despite various preparation conditions, which strongly influence the properties of alloys, most research reports the strength of Co-Cr-Mo alloy in the range of 850-1100 MPa [13-16]. A large difference can also be observed in terms of ductility, which dropped below 10% in the 3D printed sample. This can also be explained by the high concentration of grain boundaries, which prevent plastic deformation [14]. Overall, the material prepared by SLM technology showed higher strength and hardness, but lower ductility, compared to the as-cast state.

Fig. 5 Tensile stress-strain diagram for cast (a) and SLM printed (b) Co-Cr-Mo alloy.

Conclusion

This study compares the microstructure and mechanical properties of Co-Cr-Mo alloy prepared by precision casting and SLM technology. While the microstructure of the cast samples was dendritic and contained a large amount of $M_{23}C_6$ carbide particles, the samples produced by the SLM method showed a homogeneous fine-grained cellular microstructure. As a result, the printed samples also exhibited higher mechanical properties, specifically tensile yield strength of 688 ± 8 MPa and an ultimate tensile strength of 994 ± 11 MPa, compared to the as-cast state, which showed values of tensile yield strength of 457 ± 5 MPa and ultimate tensile strength of 495 ± 1 MPa. A similar trend was observed in hardness measurements, where the hardness of the printed material was approximately 15% higher. These results demonstrate the significant potential of SLM technology in the production of orthopedic implants, particularly with respect to dimensional accuracy and improved mechanical properties.

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Data Availability

The data mentioned in the present manuscript are accessible via the Zenodo repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17592298>.

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